

DCAT versus VMAT boost plans in RT planning of the Bladder cancer with the preemptive boost method.

Jeno Palvolgyi

Abstract

Aim

To reduce the MU-s to deliver the prescribed dose using a combination of dynamic conformal arcs (DCAT) with VMAT RT plan

Materials and Methods

Three plan variants were generated with the preemptive boost method for 5 Bladder cancer patients.

A: 6MV DCAT boost +6MV VMAT to PTV_4400

B: 15MV DCAT boost +15MV VMAT to PTV_4400

C: 6MV VMAT boost +6MV VMAT to PTV_4400

The boost plans and the composite plans were evaluated.

Results

The combined DCAT boost with VMAT plans (A,B) resulted in a lower total Mus compared with the 6MV VMAT (C) plans.

Introduction

With the traditional treatment planning process, in the first step, the dose planning for the low-risk and the high-risk target regions with the low risk dose prescription is performed. In the second step, the boost dose is planned and added to the base plan. While the boost dose distribution contributes to the dose distribution being at the low-risk region and being at the organs at risk (OAR) surrounding the boost region, resulting in an elevated dose compared to the prescription dose. To decrease the dose to the low-risk region, in our previous study, we proposed to reverse the planning process (preemptive boost method) [1]. In the first step, we performed the boost planning for the high-risk region as a base plane. In the second step, the composite dose to the low-risk region was planned with the base plan's bias dose. The dose distribution is different from one planned with the traditional method, in that the dose contribution of the boost to the low risk region and the surrounding OAR regions is included.

Aim

In the Bladder cancer RT treatments, the PTV_boost is oft close to the circular shape. Such targets can be covered with the prescribed dose using a variable dose rate dynamic conformal arc

field (DCAT) or VMAT fields. The present study aimed to investigate the dose distributions obtained with a combination of boost delivered with DCAT or VMAT arcs and VMAT arc to the low-risk region.

Materials and Methods

Five Bladder cancer patients, among them 2 females, were selected. 6MV and 15MV DCAT, and 6MV VMAT boost plans were generated with the Monaco 5.11 treatment planning system (Elekta BV). To produce homogenous dose distribution at the PTV_boost with sparing of the Rectum with a DCAT arc, 320-degree arcs were applied, while the VMAT fields were 180-degree arcs with 270-degree starting angles.

Three composite plan variants were generated with the boost plans as bias dose:

A: 6MV DCAT boost +6MV VMAT to PTV_4400

B: 15MV DCAT boost +15MV VMAT to PTV_4400

C: 6MV VMAT boost +6MV VMAT to PTV_4400.

The planning protocol guidelines, per protocol and variation acceptance values are summarised in Table 1.

PTVpelvis;V(95%;>);4180;3960;cGy

PTVpelvis;D(0,03ccm);<;4840;5060;cGy

PTVpelvis;V(4400cGy);>;95;90;%

PTVboost;V;95%;>;6080;5760;cGy

PTVboost;D(0,03ccm);<;7040;7360;cGy

PTVboost;V;6400;cGy;>;95;90;%

Rectum;V(3000cGy)<;50;55;%

Rectum;V(5000cGy)<;10;15;%

Femoral_Head D(0,03)<;5000;5500;cGy

Femoral_Head V(4500cGy);<;50;55;%

Bowel_Small;V(5000cGy);<;15;20;ccm

Bowel_Small;V(4500cGy);<;100;120;ccm

Bowel_Small;V(3000cGy);<;150;170;ccm

Bowel_Small;V(4000cGy);<;30;35;%

Bowel_Small;D(0.03ccm)<;5500;5700;cGy

Table 1. The protocol guidelines, per protocol, and variation acceptance levels.

The boost plan variants were compared with 3D gamma analysis performed with the Verisoft ver.6.2 (PTW Gmbh, Freiburg) software using the 3mm distance and 3% dose correspondence. Since the VMAT and the DCAT arcs were different, and the dose distributions were different outside the PTVboost, therefore the gamma analysis was limited for the PTVboost with dose suppression of 80% of the fractional prescription dose. The composite plans were analyzed with the quantities of the protocol guidelines.

Results

The results of the 3D gamma analysis of the PTVboost plans, the 6MV versus 15MV DCAT plans, and the 6MV DCAT plans versus 6MV VMAT ones are summarized in Table 2.

	6MVDCAT vs 15MVDCAT 3Dgamma index (%)	6MVDCAT vs 6MV VMAT 3Dgamma index (%)
Pt#1	90,1	69,8
Pt#2	98,9	83,4
Pt#3	96,8	93,2
Pt#4	92,9	82,6
Pt#5	98,9	85,9

Table 2. Comparison of the boost dose fields with the 3D gamma indices.

The 6 and the 15MV DCAT boost fields showed good agreement, the 3Dgamma indices were larger, than 90%, while the 3Dgamma indexes in 6MV DCAT and VMAT fields agreed over 80% , except Pt#1 with irregular PTVboost shape, shown in Fig.6. in Appendix.

Fig.1. Transversal dose distributions of the DCAT boost fields, the lateral dose profiles, and the failed points.

Fig.2. Transversal dose distributions of the VMAT boost fields, the lateral dose profiles, and the failed points.

plan				Pt#1			Pt#2			Pt#3			Pt#4			Pt#5		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
PTVboost	V	95 %	>	pp														
PTVboost	D	0.03 ccm	<	pp	va	pp	va	pp	pp	pp								
PTVboost	V	6400 cGy	>	pp	va	pp	va	va	va	va	pp	pp	pp	pp	va	pp	pp	pp
Rectum	V	3000 cGy	<	pp	pp	va	uv	pp	va	pp								
Rectum	V	5000 cGy	<	pp														
Femoral_Head_R	D	0.03 ccm	<	pp														
Femoral_Head_R	V	4500 cGy	<	pp														
Femoral_Head_R	D	0.03 ccm	<	pp														
Femoral_Head_L	V	4500 cGy	<	pp														
Femoral_Head_L	V	5000 cGy	<	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	va	pp	pp	pp	va	pp	pp	va	
Bowel_Small	V	4500 cGy	<	pp														
Bowel_Small	D	0.03 ccm	<	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	uv								
Bowel_Small	V	3000 cGy	<	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	pp	uv								
heterogeneity index				1.05	1.06	1.05	1.06	1.06	1.04	1.04	1.11	1.06	1.06	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.03	1.05

Table 3. Per protocol (pp), variation acceptance (va), and unacceptable variant (uv) in three composite plan variants.

The RT plan variants fulfilled the majority of the protocol requirements, as summarized in Table 3., only the dose to the Bowel_small showed an override, for all plan variants. The composite RT plans showed good (1.3 -1.11) heterogeneity indices of the PTVboost for all plan variants.

Fig.3. The average Rectum and Right Femur doses, and the volumes of the 3000cGy in the Bowel.

The 15MV plans (B) showed higher average dose to the Femur, while the average Rectum doses showed similar results. The volumes of the 3000cGy dose in Bowels were different.

The MU-s to deliver the prescribed dose

Fig.4. The fractional MU-s of the boost, and the composite plans, and the total MU-s of the three plan variants

plan	MU	
Pt#1	A boost	335
	A composite	1800
	A total	2135
	B boost	305
	B composite	1301
	B total	1606
Pt#2	C boost	626
	C composite	1739
	C total	2365
	A boost	277
	A composite	1158
	A total	1435
Pt#3	B boost	259
	B composite	1295
	B total	1554
	C boost	464
	C composite	1389
	C total	1863
Pt#4	A boost	264
	A composite	1277
	A total	1541
	B boost	256
	B composite	1254
	B total	1510
Pt#5	C boost	450
	C composite	1478
	C total	1928
	A boost	265
	A composite	2206
	A total	2471
Pt#5	B boost	254
	B composite	1688
	B total	1932
	C boost	504
	C composite	1844
	C total	2348
Pt#5	A boost	292
	A composite	1435
	A total	1727
	B boost	265
	B composite	1293
	B total	1458
Pt#5	C boost	642
	C composite	1700
	C total	2342

Table 4. The fractional Monitor Units of the A, B, and C treatment plan variants: the MU-s of the PTVboost plans, the PTV4400 (composite) ones, and the total MU-s.

Pt#1: corpulent male patient with irregular PTV boost shape, 6MV plans (A,C) are delivered with high MU-s, while plan (B) showed the lower MU-s.

Pt#2: male patient with regular PTVboost shape

Pt#3: female patient with regular PTVboost shape. The dose distributions of the three RT plan variants and the DVH-s are illustrated in the Appendix.

Pt#4: male patient with regular PTVboost shape and with hip prosthesis. The increased dose restrictions to the Femurs resulted in high MU-s in all plan variants.

Pt#5: female patient with regular PTV boost shape

Pt#2 and Pt#3 and Pt#5: the corresponding plan variants showed similar MU-s.

Conclusion

All the plan variants were found suitable for the RT treatments. The combined DCAT boost with VMAT plan (A,B) resulted in a lower total fractional MU-s by 300-800 MU-s, compared with the 6MV VMAT (C) plans.

Reference

[1.] J. Palvolgyi: Radiotherapy treatment planning with preemptive boost method. Preliminary results

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6624247](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6624247)

APPENDIX

Fig.5. Plan review of the A,B, and C RT plan variants and DVH curves of Pt#3.

Fig.6. Dose comparison of the 6MV DCAT and the VMAT boost fields of Pt#1 with an irregular Bladder shape

